

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 30/03/2026

Accepted: 06/05/2026

Published: 20/05/2026

Citation: Jayasree P, Padmanabha Reddy A, Nagaveni K, Mahagaonkar P (2026) Artificial Neural Networks with Different Activation Functions to Solve Higher-Order Ordinary Differential Equations. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 19(19): 1300-1309. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v19i19.484>

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Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.isee.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Artificial Neural Networks with Different Activation Functions to Solve Higher-Order Ordinary Differential Equations

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Abstract

Objectives: To make (i) a systematic assessment of activation functions for solving initial value problems (IVPs) and ii) the use of Automatic Differentiation (AD) for accurate gradient evaluation in Gradient Descent (GD). **Method:** Unlike conventional backpropagation approaches that rely on manually derived gradients, the proposed AD-based framework enables precise derivative evaluation using the chain rule, improving numerical stability and convergence efficiency. The performance of the proposed method is validated through several benchmark higher-order IVP test problems and compared with existing numerical techniques including Regression-Based Weight initialization (RBW), Chebyshev Wavelet Collocation Method (CWCM), and Haar Wavelet Collocation Method (HWCM). **Findings:** In the present study, an enhanced ANN-based methodology incorporating Automatic Differentiation (AD) is developed to solve higher-order initial value problems (IVPs) with improved accuracy and convergence. The numerical experiments indicate that the proposed ANN-AD approach achieves maximum absolute errors, depending on the order and complexity of the test problems. In several benchmark cases, the method consistently attains errors below 10^{-6} , demonstrating superior approximation accuracy compared to existing ANN-based approaches reported in the literature. Furthermore, the proposed method exhibits stable convergence behaviour across first, second and fifth-order IVPs without requiring problem-specific tuning. These results confirm that the proposed methodology provides an accurate, flexible and computationally efficient framework for solving higher-order differential equations. Additionally, its robustness and generalization capability suggest strong potential for extension to more complex boundary value problems and nonlinear differential systems in future work. **Novelty:** This work combines Automatic Differentiation-driven gradient optimization with activation-function sensitivity analysis in a unified ANN framework for higher-order IVPs, a combination not systematically explored previously.

Keywords: Differential equations; Neural network; Activation function; Automatic differentiation; Gradient descent

1 Introduction

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have emerged as an effective computational framework for solving differential equations by transforming them into optimization problems. Unlike traditional numerical methods, ANN-based approaches provide continuous approximate solutions over the entire solution domain without requiring discretization of derivatives. This property makes them particularly attractive for solving higher-order ordinary differential equations (ODEs), where classical numerical schemes often involve increased computational complexity and stability challenges.

ANN architectures are inspired by the structural and functional mechanisms of biological neurons. In artificial neurons, input signals are multiplied by weights, combined with bias terms, and processed through activation functions to generate outputs. Mathematically, the transformation performed at each hidden neuron can be expressed as

$$z_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} t_j + u_i$$

followed by the activation mapping

$$s(z_i) = s \left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} t_j + u_i \right),$$

and the final network output

$$y = \sum_{i=1}^m v_i s(z_i).$$

Here, w_{ij} and v_i denote connection weights, u_i represents bias parameters and s is the activation function that introduces nonlinearity into the model.

The application of ANN techniques to differential equations was first introduced by Lagaris et al.⁽¹⁾, who formulated the solution of ordinary and partial differential equations as unconstrained optimization problems. Later, Chakraverty and Mall⁽²⁾, proposed regression-based ANN approaches for solving ordinary differential equations and investigated the influence of weight initialization strategies⁽³⁾ and Gaussian Radial Basis function (GRBF) approximation model by Roseline N et al.⁽⁴⁾. Alternative numerical techniques such as the Chebyshev Wavelet Collocation Method (CWCM)⁽⁵⁾, Haar Wavelet Collocation Method (HWCM)⁽⁶⁾ and Variational Iteration Method (VIM) have also been developed to improve approximation accuracy for higher-order problems. Despite these developments, two important challenges remain insufficiently explored in the existing literature. First, most ANN-based differential equation solvers rely on conventional backpropagation techniques that require explicit gradient derivations, which may reduce computational efficiency and introduce implementation complexity for higher-order problems. Second, although activation functions play a critical role in determining approximation capability and convergence behaviour of neural networks, their systematic performance evaluation in solving higher-order initial value problems (IVPs) has received limited attention. To address these challenges, the present study develops an ANN-based computational framework incorporating Automatic Differentiation (AD)⁽⁷⁾ for accurate gradient evaluation within the Gradient Descent (GD) optimization process. Unlike numerical and symbolic differentiation techniques, AD applies the chain rule directly to computational graphs, enabling efficient and stable derivative computation without truncation or round-off errors. In addition, the influence of different activation functions on solution accuracy and convergence behaviour is systematically investigated for higher-order ODE-based IVPs.

2 Methodology

The proposed methodology builds upon the foundational work of Isaac E. Lagaris et al.⁽¹⁾, who first formulated the solution of differential equations using Artificial Neural Networks by transforming them into **unconstrained optimization problems**. This approach was further extended by Susmita Mall and S. Chakraverty⁽³⁾ through the **introduction of regression-based algorithms combined with backpropagation for improved weight initialization and convergence**. In this study, the proposed ANN framework **incorporates Automatic Differentiation (AD) to enhance gradient computation accuracy and training efficiency**. The performance of the method is evaluated by varying key parameters, **including activation functions, network architecture and the order of differential equations**. The proposed approach is tested on benchmark **first, second and fifth-order initial value problems**. For validation, the obtained numerical solutions are compared with exact solutions, and performance

is assessed using maximum absolute error and convergence behaviour. Additionally, the results are compared with existing ANN-based methods reported in the literature^{(3), (5), (6)} and the comparisons (shown in Figures 4, 6 and 8) demonstrate improvements in accuracy and stability.

2.1 Dataset Description and Training Inputs

Unlike conventional machine-learning applications that rely on externally collected datasets, ANN-based differential equation solvers generate training samples directly from the computational domain of the governing equation. In this study, the dataset consists of collocation points uniformly sampled from the solution interval $t \in [l, m]$ for each test problem. These collocation points serve as input features for the neural network, while the analytical solutions corresponding to the governing equations are used for validation purposes only (not for supervised training).

For each benchmark example:

- the domain interval $[l, m]$ selected according to the problem definition,
- n collocation points are generated uniformly within the interval,
- initial conditions are embedded directly into the trial solution to enforce solution consistency.

2.2 Neural Network Architecture and Parameters

A feed-forward neural network (FFNN) with a single input layer, one hidden layer, and one output layer is employed to approximate the solution of higher-order IVPs. The network architecture is defined as follows and shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1. The Mathematical model of single hidden layer ANN

- Input variable: independent variable t
- Hidden neurons: m
- Output variable: approximate solution $x_s(t, q)$

- Trainable parameters: weights and biases q

The activation functions considered in this study include:

- ReLU
- Leaky ReLU
- Maxout
- Swish
- Sigmoid
- Tanh
- SSLU
- MishReLU
- S-Parabola

These activation functions shown in Figure 2 were selected based on recommendations from recent literature [8 - 14] to evaluate their convergence behaviour and approximation capability in solving higher-order ODEs. The optimization of network parameters is performed using the Gradient Descent (GD) algorithm with gradients computed through Automatic Differentiation (AD) instead of conventional backpropagation.

Fig 2. Different Activation functions

2.3 Trial Solution Formulation

To ensure that the approximate solution satisfies the prescribed initial conditions exactly, a trial solution of the following form is constructed:

$$x_s(t, q) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} C_i t^i + (t-l)^n N(t, q)$$

Here

- C_i represent initial-condition constants,
- $N(t, q)$ denotes the neural-network output,
- q represents adjustable network parameters.

This formulation guarantees that the ANN approximation satisfies all initial conditions by construction.

2.4 Automatic Differentiation-Based Gradient Computation

Automatic Differentiation (AD) is employed to compute higher-order derivatives required in the governing differential equation. Unlike numerical differentiation methods that introduce truncation errors or symbolic differentiation approaches that increase algebraic complexity⁽⁶⁾, AD applies the chain rule directly to the computational graph, ensuring accurate derivative evaluation with improved numerical stability.

The derivatives

$$x_s^{(1)}(t, q), x_s^{(2)}(t, q), \dots, x_s^{(n)}(t, q)$$

are computed efficiently using AD and incorporated into the residual minimization process.

2.5 Cost Function Formulation

The neural network parameters are optimized by minimizing the residual error associated with the governing differential equation. The cost function is defined as

$$E(t, q) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{d^n x_s(t_i, q)}{dt^n} - h \left(t_i, x_s(t_i, q), \frac{dx_s(t_i, q)}{dt}, \dots, \frac{d^{n-1} x_s(t_i, q)}{dt^{n-1}} \right) \right)^2$$

Here

- n denotes the number of collocation points,
- t_i represents training points within the solution domain.

The cost function is minimized using the Gradient Descent algorithm.

2.6 Validation Procedure and Benchmark Comparisons

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed method, ANN-generated solutions are compared with:

- analytical (exact) solutions
- Regression-Based Weight initialization (RBW) method
- Chebyshev Wavelet Collocation Method (CWCM)
- Variational Iteration Method (VIM)
- Haar Wavelet Collocation Method (HWCM)

These approaches serve as gold-standard benchmark techniques for performance comparison.

2.7 Evaluation Metrics

Solution accuracy is assessed using the following quantitative error measures:

Maximum Absolute Error (MAE)

$$\max |x_{\text{exact}}(t) - x_{\text{ANN}}(t)|$$

These metrics provide reliable indicators of approximation accuracy across the solution domain.

2.8 Experimental Controls and Reproducibility

To ensure reliability and reproducibility of results, the following implementation controls are adopted:

- uniform collocation-point sampling across solution intervals
- identical network architecture across activation-function comparisons
- identical stopping criteria for Gradient Descent optimization
- consistent initialization strategy for network parameters
- Automatic Differentiation used for all derivative computations
- implementation performed using Python with Autograd library

These controls ensure that performance differences observed between activation functions arise solely from their approximation characteristics rather than experimental variability.

3 Results and Discussion

From Table 1, it is evident that the performance of activation functions is **problem-dependent rather than uniform**. For **Example 1**, the **Sigmoid** activation function achieves the lowest error (**0.000306**). This can be attributed to the smooth and bounded nature of the Sigmoid function, which is well-suited for approximating exponential-type solutions such as $x(t) = e^t$. In contrast, piecewise-linear activations like ReLU exhibit larger errors due to their limited capability in capturing smooth curvature.

In **Example 2**, **ReLU** produces a less error (**1.33227e-15**) indicating near machine precision. This superior performance may be due to the polynomial nature of the exact solution $x(t) = t^4 - t^3$, which can be efficiently approximated using piecewise-linear basis functions. This observation aligns with findings in existing studies such as⁽⁵⁾, where neural networks demonstrated strong performance for polynomial-type differential equations.

However, in **Example 3** which involves a fifth-order differential equation with oscillatory behaviour, **Leaky ReLU** outperforms other activation functions with a significantly lower error (**4.14574e-05**). This suggests that allowing small negative slopes helps improve approximation in problems involving trigonometric components. Notably, Tanh performs poorly in this case (error = 0.221081) indicating that saturation effects may hinder its ability to model higher-order oscillatory dynamics.

Table 1. Performance of AFs applied to three test problems

Test problems AFs	ReLU	Leaky-ReLU	Maxout	Swish	Sigmoid	Tanh	SSLU	MishReLU	S-Parabola
1	0.186827	0.007549	0.20741	0.00374	0.000306	0.001919	0.0195996	0.0137968	0.00485711
2	1.33227e-15	0.022597	0.032976	0.030020	0.032976	0.000383	0.000974	0.000172	0.008523
3	0.037867	4.14574e-05	0.001282	0.000818	0.003687	0.221081	0.058675	0.0454955	0.0369126

A key observation across all three problems is that no single activation function consistently outperforms others. Although Tanh shows relatively stable performance across multiple cases, it fails in higher-order problems, highlighting the importance of selecting activation functions based on problem characteristics.

From a comparative perspective, earlier works such as^{(1), (2), (3), (4), (8), (9), (10), (11), (12), (13), (14)} primarily focused on solving individual differential equations using a **single activation function** and did not systematically analyze the impact of multiple activation functions across different types of IVPs. Furthermore, most existing approaches rely on numerical differentiation, which may introduce approximation errors.

Research Gap Identified:

There is a lack of comprehensive studies that:

- compare multiple activation functions
- across different orders of differential equations
- utilize Automatic Differentiation

Fundamental Contribution of the Present Work:

The present study addresses this gap by:

- systematically investigate **nine activation functions**
- applying them to **first, second and fifth-order IVPs**
- integrating **Automatic Differentiation**, which improves accuracy and avoids numerical approximation errors

Overall, the results demonstrate that the proposed ANN-AD framework is not only accurate but also flexible, with performance strongly influenced by the choice of activation function and the nature of the differential equation.

Example 1: Consider a typical differential equation that models Exponential growth⁽³⁾

$$x^{(i)} = \alpha x(t) \quad (1)$$

subjected to the initial condition $x(0) = 1$ for $\alpha = 1$, exact result is $x(t) = e^t$, $t \in [0, 1]$. The network was trained on 10 equally spaced points within the interval $[0, 1]$, with configurations of 4, 5 and 6 nodes. Results for the 6-node setup, utilizing nine different activation functions are visualized in Figure 3 (Showing the performance of Sigmoid, remaining 8 results are provided in Table 1). The error analysis for this case is depicted in Figure 4.

Fig 3. Exact and ANN result of Example 1

Fig 4. Error plot between Exact and NN arbitrary, RBW, and AD methods

Example 2: Lane-Emden Equation⁽⁵⁾

$$x^{(ii)} = -\frac{2}{t}x^{(i)} - x(t) + t^3 + t^2 + 12t + 6 \tag{2}$$

Subject to, $x(0) = 0, x^{(i)}(0) = 0$, exact result is $x(t) = t^4 - t^3, t \in [0, 1]$. The problem under consideration is a second-order non-homogeneous singular IVP. The network was trained using 16 collocation points in the domain $[0, 1]$ with outcomes obtained by adding nine different activation functions, plotted in Figure 5 (illustrating the performance of ReLU, remaining 8 are presented in Table 1). A comparison of the results is shown in Figure 6.

Example 3: Induction motor problem⁽⁶⁾

$$x^{(v)} = 5(t-1)\sin t + 5(t-t^2-5)\cos t - tx \tag{3}$$

with the given initial conditions $x(0) = 5, x^{(i)}(0) = -5, x^{(ii)}(0) = -5, x^{(iii)}(0) = 15, x^{(iv)}(0) = 5,$

Fig 5. Exact and ANN result of Example 2

Fig 6. Comparison between computed and Exact results Example 2

exact result is $x(t) = 5(t - 1) \cos t, t \in [0, 1]$. We trained the problem using 10 points within the domain $[0, 1]$ applying nine different AFs. The results are visualized in Figure 7 (Showing performance of Leaky ReLU, remaining 8 results are provided in Table 1) Comparison of the results for this example is illustrated in Figure 8.

4 Conclusion

In this study, an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) framework incorporating Automatic Differentiation (AD) was developed to solve special higher-order initial value problems (IVPs). The effectiveness of the proposed approach was demonstrated through three benchmark examples involving first, second and fifth-order ordinary differential equations. The numerical results demonstrate that the proposed AD-based ANN method achieves highly accurate approximations with maximum absolute errors of small order (typically between 10^{-3} to 10^{-15}), confirming its reliability when compared with existing techniques such as RBW, CWCM and HWCM. Another important contribution of this work is the systematic evaluation of nine activation functions for solving higher-order IVPs within a unified ANN framework. The experimental results indicate that the Sigmoid activation function performed best for Example 1, ReLU for Example 2, and Leaky ReLU for Example 3, demonstrating that

Fig 7. Exact and ANN result of Example 3

Fig 8. Comparison of Haar results with ANN results Example 3

activation-function performance depends strongly on the structure and complexity of the governing differential equation. These findings highlight the importance of activation-function selection in improving ANN approximation accuracy for differential equation solvers. The novelty of the present work lies in the integration of Automatic Differentiation with Gradient Descent optimization for higher-order IVPs together with a comparative activation-function sensitivity study. Based on the obtained results, it is recommended that activation-function selection should be treated as a problem-dependent design parameter when applying ANN methods to higher-order ODEs. In particular, rectified linear activation families (ReLU) are suitable for certain nonlinear structures, while sigmoid-type activation functions may provide improved convergence behaviour for smoother solution profiles.

Future work can extend the proposed methodology to:

- Nonlinear boundary value problems,
- System of differential equations, Stochastic differential equations,
- Solution of partial differential equations using physics-informed neural networks,

- Solution of differential equations using Kolmogorov-Arnold networks (KAN).

Overall, the proposed AD-based ANN framework provides an accurate, flexible, and computationally efficient approach for solving higher-order ordinary differential equations and offers promising potential for broader applications in scientific computing and engineering analysis.

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